

Title:

Creatine supplementation and effects in Hot climates

Abstract:

Creatine supplementation has gained popularity among gym-goers particularly in hot climates where dehydration risks are elevated. This literature review examines the creatine use, renal stress and renal health through analysis of recent scientific literature, it is clear that inadequate hydration during creatine supplementation in high temperature regions may increase renal stress markers like creatinine and urea. This paper also discusses the role of education in promoting safe supplementation practices, especially in regions with limited health literacy. Recommendations include proper dosing guidelines and emphasized hydration protocols for athletes in hot regions.

Introduction:

Creatine is a naturally occurring nitrogenous organic acid that plays a fundamental role in metabolism, particularly in muscle and brain [tissue](#). It is synthesized endogenously from amino acids and is also obtained exogenously through dietary sources specifically through red meat and seafood. Importantly, it is difficult to saturate Creatine stores within muscles through diet alone. So people take creatine exogenously. Creatine is primarily stored as phosphocreatine within cells. It improves intense, short duration exercises by providing short rapid bursts of energy. It also supports rapid regeneration of ATP and enhance neuromuscular activity. As a result muscles don't tire fast and exercise duration lasts longer till exhaustion hits.

Due to its role in increased performance, creatine supplementation- most commonly in the form of creatine monohydrate- has become one of the most popular nutrition among athletes, gym-goers and bodybuilders worldwide. It has proven benefits are increased muscle mass, strength gains and neuroprotective effects. Its widespread use is due to its above proven benefits.

However, this widespread use often outpaces comprehensive public understanding. As a result, a knowledge gap exist regarding creatine dosage and environmental conditions. In Hot climates, the human body already undergoes thermoregulatory strain, increased body temperature and increased water loss through sweating. This state of increased dehydration risk presents a unique challenge for creatine users.

Hydration and Heat Stress

In hot climates, drinking enough water is important to reduce stress on the body caused by heavy sweating and supplement use. Heat-safety guidelines suggest drinking about 240 mL (8 oz) of fluid every 15–20 minutes when exposed to high temperatures for long

periods. Total daily fluid intake should also be increased in hot conditions to replace fluid lost through sweat, depending on activity level and the environment.

Methodology:

This section explains how I conducted my research, which includes a review of existing literature and a pilot survey.

Literature Review Method:

I wanted to find and summarize all the best available science on my topic. Here is how I did it:

Where I searched:

I used Google Scholar, Pubmed and ScienceDirect. I read these studies to find common facts, ideas and gaps in knowledge about creatine use in the heat.

Keywords I used:

I searched for words like “creatine supplementation”, “hot climates”, “dehydration”, “kidney stress,” and “exercise”.

Survey method:

To get real-world opinion, I created a survey. I made the survey using Google Forms. The goal was to understand what gym-goers know about creatine dosage and hydration in hot weather. I shared the survey online on platforms like Survey swap and Reddit to reach the people who go to the gym.

Results

A total of 52 people took part in the survey. Most participants (67.3%) were aged 18–24, followed by those under 18 (23.1%). Just over half of the respondents (51.9%) reported living in a hot or warm climate. Regarding creatine use, 44.2% said they currently use creatine, while 40.4% had used it in the past, showing that creatine use was common among participants.

Among the 29 participants who had used creatine, most received their information from informal sources. About 41.4% relied on social media, and 37.9% depended on gym trainers or coaches, while only a small number used scientific or research-based sources. Knowledge about correct creatine dosage varied, with many participants believing the recommended daily dose was higher than standard guidelines. Although most users (75.9%) correctly understood that water intake should increase when using creatine in hot weather, daily water intake still differed, with some drinking less than 2 liters per day.

Many users reported side effects while using creatine. Around half experienced dehydration, cramps, or bloating occasionally, while over one-third experienced these symptoms frequently. During hotter seasons, some participants increased both their water intake and adjusted their creatine dose, but a small group made no changes at all.

When asked about possible risks of using creatine in hot climates, most participants identified kidney strain or dehydration as the main concerns. An attention-check question was passed by most respondents, suggesting that the survey responses were generally reliable. Overall, the results show gaps in knowledge about correct dosing, mixed hydration habits, and heavy reliance on non-scientific information among young creatine users living in warm climates.

Discussion

The results of this study show that creatine is commonly used by young gym-goers, especially in hot or warm climates. Most users get their information from social media or gym trainers instead of scientific sources. This may be one reason why many participants were unsure about the correct creatine dose and often believed that higher doses were needed. Using higher doses than recommended can increase the chance of side effects, especially in hot weather.

Even though most participants knew they should drink more water when using creatine in hot conditions, many still experienced problems such as dehydration, muscle cramps, and bloating. This suggests that knowing about hydration is not always enough, and that people may still not be drinking enough water. Many users were worried about dehydration and kidney strain, but some did not change their creatine use or water intake during hotter seasons. This shows a gap between what people know and what they actually do. Better education and clearer guidance could help reduce these risks.

Conclusion

This study shows that creatine use is common among young people, but many lack clear knowledge about correct dosing and proper hydration, especially in hot climates. While most users are aware that drinking more water is important, many still experience dehydration-related symptoms. Relying on non-scientific sources for information may contribute to these issues. Providing simple, clear, and reliable information about safe creatine use and hydration could help gym-goers use creatine more safely in hot environments.

References

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